

time in the grains indicated that *R. oryzae* is a seedborne pathogen and that infested seeds may serve as a primary source of inoculum.

R. oryzae usually grew over or dominated other associated organisms on

PDA. Sometimes it grew in mixed culture with other fast-growing fungi, or formed distinct individual colonies side by side with colonies of other organisms. Other fungal species that were commonly encountered during the study, in the

order of their frequency of isolation, were *Fusarium*, *Curvularia*, *Nigrospora*, *Helminthosporium*, *Phoma*, *Cercospora*, and other unidentified and non-sporulating fungi. ■

Rice ragged stunt disease in China

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In March 1979, the senior author found in 3 lines of hybrid rice about 60 hills infected by a disease in an experimental plot in Zhonghwa country, Guangdong, PROC. The diseased plants were stunted and their leaves were green but ragged and twisted.

The diseased hills were transplanted in pots and kept at GAAS. At later growth stages, their flag leaves were short, distorted, and occasionally ragged. Numerous nodal panicles were produced but many were incompletely exerted and most of the grains were empty (see figure). A few swollen veins were found on the lower surface of leaf blades and the outer surface of leaf sheaths. All the symptoms were similar to those of rice ragged stunt disease in the Philippines.

Brown planthoppers *Nilaparvata lugens* were confined on diseased plants for acquisition feeding. The viruliferous

A rice hill infected with ragged stunt disease in China.

insects were then used to inoculate healthy seedlings, which then developed the above-mentioned symptoms, indicating that brown planthoppers could transmit the disease.

The results identify the symptoms of the disease found in Zhonghwa as those of rice ragged stunt in the Philippines. This may be the first record of ragged stunt in China. ■

Effectiveness of fungicides in the control of blast (neck rot)

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No suitable chemicals to control blast (neck rot) infection caused by *Piricularia oryzae* has been reported in Uttar Pradesh. Therefore the relative effectiveness of some fungicides was tested in the field.

Foliar sprays of four fungicides — edifenphos, Miltox, blue copper, and

Relative effectiveness of some fungicides on blast (neck rot) incidence and grain yield of paddy during kharif seasons of 1974–75 and 1975–76.

Fungicide	Dose (% active ingredient)	Blast (neck rot) incidence (%) (mean of 4 replicates)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
		1974–75	1975–76	1974–75	1975–76
Edifenphos	0.1	2.1	2.8	3.3	3.4
Miltox	0.25	4.3	5.4	3.0	2.9
Blue copper	0.30	7.0	6.0	2.7	2.2
Kitazin 17%	988 kg/ha	10.0	8.6	2.1	1.9
Control	—	12.6	10.3	1.7	1.4
C.D. @5% (critical deviation)		2.2%	2.45	2.20	4.25

Kitazin—were tested on the susceptible variety Basmati 370 in a randomized

block design. Fertilizer was applied at 80 kg N/ha. Spraying was done 25, 35,

40, and 60 days after transplanting.

The results of 2 years' (1974-75 and 1975-76) experiments indicate that all fungicides reduced the infection and increased yields (see table). Edifenphos

was most effective. Similar findings were also reported by Mohanti and Dash in 1971 and Subramanian and Ramaswamy in 1973. Miltox and blue copper were also good.

exposed to natural infection in the blast nursery. Ten days later the number of blast-infected plants and their lesion numbers were recorded.

With artificial inoculation disease incidence was greatest on KTH 17 (see table). The percentage of infection on this variety was highest (44.5%) on Bulacan phosphorus-deficient soil. Disease incidence ranged from 0 to 4% on Tetep and from 0 to 9% on IR442. I-2017 was not pathogenic on Carreon, which remained disease-free regardless of soil type.

Under natural infection, IR442 exhibited greater disease incidence in different soils than Tetep or KTH 17. That was expected because IR442 was used as the spreader source of inoculum in the blast nursery and most of the fungus populations present were pathogenic on it. KTH 17 produced more lesions than IR442 and Tetep with artificial inoculation in different soil types but in the blast nursery IR442 had more lesions than either KTH 17 or Tetep. Carreon remained disease-free in both instances, suggesting varietal differences in blast reaction.

Under natural conditions, disease incidence was high in Bulacan potassium-deficient, Malinao iron-toxic, and Pangil peat soil (see table). Disease incidence in susceptible varieties was greater on those soils, and least in the San Pablo zinc-deficient soil. That could be due to

Rice blast incidence in different soil types

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The evidence indicating increased blast susceptibility of rice when the soil nitrogen content is high seems conclusive, although the disease severity varies with other soil and climatic factors. The ratio of one element to another and the physical and chemical properties of the soil may play an important role in disease development. Numerous experiments from different countries have indicated that high soil nitrogen increases blast severity regardless of available phosphorus or potassium. That indicates that the influence of other elements is not significant. The influence of nitrogen on blast disease development under different soil conditions was evaluated to determine if varietal reactions to the

disease were affected.

Seven soils were obtained from various Philippine sites and designated by location as Malinao (Fe toxicity), Bulacan (K deficiency), Pangil (P deficiency), San Pablo (Zn deficiency), Pangil peat, Luisiana (P deficiency), and Maahas clay (normal check). The rice varieties used were Carreon, Tetep, IR442, and KTH 17. Carreon is resistant and the latter three varieties are highly susceptible to blast fungus isolate I-2017.

The soils were placed in plastic trays and 5 g ammonium sulfate was incorporated into each. Seeds were sown in four randomized rows. The plants were inoculated in the dew chamber with blast fungus isolate I-2017 that had been grown on prune agar for 18 days. At 24 hours after inoculation, the plants were transferred to the glasshouse (20-36°C) where a humidifier provided dew. Seven days after inoculation disease incidence was scored and the lesions (Types 3 and 4) on the infected plants were counted. Another set of varieties grown in trays with the different soil types were

Disease incidence and severity on four rice varieties in different soil types. IRRI, 1979.^a

Soil, disorder, series	Inoculated with I-2017								Natural infection							
	Carreon		Tetep		IR442		KTH 17		Carreon		Tetep		IR442		KTH 17	
	DI (%)	L/L	DI (70)	L/L	DI (%)	L/L	DI (%)	L/L	DI (%)	L/L	DI (%)	L/L	DI (%)	L/L	DI (%)	L/L
Bulacan (K deficient), Buonavista sandy clay loam	0	0	2.5	0	0	0	44.4	0.9	0	0	11	0.2	89	4.0	57	1.0
Maahas clay (normal), Lipa loam	0	0	2.5	0.3	5.5	0.4	34.5	2.7	0	0	22	0.2	92	4.9	52	1.7
Malinao (Fe toxicity), Malinao fine sandy loam	0	0	0	0	7	0.2	19.0	0.8	0	0	4.5	0	91	4.2	48	1.3
Pangil peat - Histosol from Pangil, Laguna	0	0	0	0	9	0	16.5	0.7	0	0	11.5	9.0	89	2.5	23	0.6
Luisiana (P deficient), Luisiana clay loam	0	0	4	0.5	2.5	0	12.5	1.0	0	0	13.5	0.5	78	2.3	24	0.5
Pangil (P deficient), Paete clay loam	0	0	3	0	4.0	0.3	10.0	1.0	0	0	14.0	0.3	89	2.7	31	0.9
San Pablo (Zn deficient) Lipa loam	0	0	0	0	4.5	0	8.0	0.9	0	0	8.0	0	51	1.6	11	0.7

^aDI = disease incidence, L/L = mean number of lesions per leaf.